

Motivational Factors and Its Effects on Teachers' Performance in Selected Campuses of a Private Educational System

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Abstract

Motivating employees to do well at their jobs is vital, as it is through their efforts that the goals of organizations are achieved. Accordingly, this study was conducted to determine the motivational factors and its effect on teachers' performance in selected campuses of a private educational system. This study, a quantitative type of research that used descriptive design, is focused on the motivational factors in a private educational system which were assessed by 129 teacher-respondents using an adapted questionnaire. The descriptive data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentage, weighted mean, and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Pearson Correlation (Pearson r) test. Majority of the teacher-respondents are 20-30 years old, single, college graduate, and have only rendered five years and below. Regardless of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service, the teacher-respondents' assessment on the motivational factors showed that the motivation and hygiene factors motivate them at a high extent. Moreover, the single and married teacher-respondents were motivated at a high extent while the separated ones were motivated at a very high extent. The teachers' performance in all the three campuses were all very satisfactory. The results of this study revealed that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation and Hygiene factors when grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service. On the other hand, it was found out that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on these factors when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Also, the results of this study also revealed that there is no significant relationship between the motivational factors and the teachers' performance. A faculty development plan to enhance the teaching performance of the teachers was the output of this study.

Keywords: *motivational factors, teacher's performance, principals*

Introduction

The fulfillment of any organization's goals and objectives lies in the abilities of the top management to appropriately classify measures that would ensure constant greater productivity and a comfortable working relationship between management and the employees. According to Acheck (2015), one of the effective tools in boosting productivity and commitment among members of an organization could be motivation. Motivating employees to do well at their jobs is vital, as it is through their efforts that the goals of organizations are achieved.

The literature presents different motivational strategies that are often adapted from the various motivational theories claimed by different theoreticians. Although the literature is affluent with motivation theories and its strategies, the problem is that most of them fall short of practical application. In applying these motivational strategies, a manager should note that understanding what people need gives signs to understanding them. For example, an employee who is trying to satisfy esteem needs may feel thankful when his supervisor praises an achievement. However, another employee who is trying to satisfy social needs may dislike being praised in front of peers if the praise sets the individual apart from the rest of the group. In schools where principals are the main administrators of both staff and students, the motivational factors and the ways they are employed could possibly make an impact on the attainment of the organizational goals, either positively or negatively. These motivational factors are often adapted and implemented in the form of rules, reforms, and regulations that guide the institution. According to Saeed and Muneer (2012), secondary school administrators have in most cases made use of motivation in order to boost the morale of both staff and students in the teaching and learning process, thereby promoting high quality and output. It has been observed many times that employees who are satisfied with their jobs are still not good performers. This may be because of their lack of motivation and commitment to the organization. Ellis (as cited in Ukpong & Unchendu 2012) who carried out a study on "motivating teachers for excellence" concluded that teachers were primarily motivated within the school system by intrinsic rewards such as self-respect, responsibility, and sense of accomplishment, praise, and commendations. This implies that school administrators can boost morale and motivate teachers to excel by means of participatory governance, in-service education, and systematic supportive evaluation. Callo (2015) considered teachers' performance as one of the most important components in academic functions. As an output, the effectiveness or efficiency of performance may be attributed to how much an individual teacher in the school is motivated to perform his tasks well.

Accordingly, this study aimed to determine the motivational factors and its effect on teachers' performance in selected campuses of a private educational system. From a total of nine campuses, this study only focused on three campuses. These campuses are considered big campuses. To be classified as a big campus, it should have at least 30 teachers and over 1000 students from Pre-school to Senior High School. The Faculty Performance Report, which were provided by each principal, were used by the researcher to determine the teachers' performance. There were ten (10) performance indicators that were used in this study. These are the observation rating, participation in activities, attendance, outstanding accomplishments, seminars attended, external marketing efforts, submission of requirements, students' achievement, and students' evaluation, and, personality traits. The results of this study served as a basis for the enhancement of management development programs that could enhance the teachers' performance, specifically on the outstanding accomplishments and attendance in seminars.

This study was anchored on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. This theory states that there are two separate sets of factors that influence motivation. One set is called maintenance (or hygiene) factors because they must not be ignored. They are potent dissatisfiers and can cause negative feelings to employees. The other set of factors, called motivational factors, is comprised of the real satisfiers, and therefore the ones that actually motivate people in the workplace. (Camilar-Serano, 2016). Herzberg's Theory became the basis for why companies emphasize the continuous development of their employees. Yet, in developing countries like the Philippines, the pay is an important motivating factor for work. Pay differentials may influence the motivation of the people in the workplace (Quero, 2017). With this kind of set up in the Philippines, this theory can be a useful support to managers because it points out that improving the environment in which the job is performed goes only so far in motivating employees. The researcher believes that focusing mainly on hygiene factors will not be satisfactory, and managers should also improve jobs by giving employees breaks for challenging work, greater responsibilities, advancement opportunities, and a job in which their subordinates can feel victorious.

Figure 1. Model Concept of the Two-Factor Theory on Teacher's Performance

Figure 1 represents the model concept of the study. The Hygiene Factors arrow consists of Status; Relationship with supervisors, peers, and subordinates; Quality of Supervision; Company policy and administrations; Job security; Working conditions; and, Pay. The hygiene factors are believed to decrease the performance of the workers in the workplace. On the other hand, the Motivational Factors arrow consists of Work itself; Achievement; Possibility of growth; Responsibility; Advancement; and, Recognition. These factors are said to increase the performance of the workers in the workplace. The figure further suggests that administrators need to understand that apart from making available motivators for their subordinates, they must equally ensure that they put in place the hygiene factors because, even though their presence does not motivate, their absence will limit the output of teachers. This can be done by having a policy manual on motivational factors for teachers' performance.

Methods

Research Design

This study is a quantitative type of research that used descriptive design since it only determined the motivational factors and its effects on the teachers' performance in selected campuses of a private educational system. According to Francisco, Francisco, and Arlos (2016), descriptive research describes what exists and may be able to help uncover new facts and meanings. It seeks to describe the current status of an unidentified variable, provide systematic information about a phenomenon, and observe subjects without intervention.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 129 Preschool to Senior High School teachers from the big campuses of SFAC (Bacoor, Las Piñas, Taguig). Majority or 80 (about 62%) of the teacher-respondents belong to the age 20 – 30 age group. In addition, 21 (about 26%) belong to 41 – 50; 15 (about 12%) belong to 51 – 60; 13 (about 10%) belong to 31 – 40 age group. Majority or 85 (about 66%) of the teacher-respondents are Single; 42 (about 33%) are Married; and 2 (about 2%) are Separated. Majority or 105 (about 81%) of the teacher-respondents are College Graduate; 19 (about 15%) are with Master's Units; 4 (about 3%) are Master's Graduate, and 1(1%) has Doctorate Units. Majority or 86 (about 67%) of the teacher-respondents belong to the 5 years and below bracket. 20 (about 16%) rendered 21 or more years serving the institution; 12 (about 9%) rendered 16 – 20 years; 6 (about 5%) rendered 11 – 15 years; and 5 (about 4%) rendered 6 – 10 years serving the institution.

Instrumentation

The researcher adapted a questionnaire which was formulated in Survey Monkey, an American based company. The researcher modified the questionnaire by adding a checklist to it and transforming it into two parts. The format of the questionnaire started with an introductory part of the questionnaire which asked participants about their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, and length of service in school. The second consists of distinct statements each measuring Herzberg's Motivation factors and Hygiene factors. The first fold part measures the Motivation factors according to Herzberg's Two-Factor theory. This part consists of five subscales measuring achievement (consisting 3 questions), advancement (2 questions), work itself (3 questions), recognition (3 questions), and growth (3 questions) and as suggested earlier, responses were recorded on a four-point Likert scale from '1' for Very Low Extent and '4' for Very High Extent. The second fold part measures the Maintenance or Hygiene factors from Herzberg's theory where this part of the questionnaire consists of six subscales measuring company policy (3 questions), relationship with peers (3questions), work security (3 questions), relationship with supervisor (3 questions), money (2 questions), and working conditions (2 questions) and their responses were also recorded on a four- point Likert rating scale from '1' for Very Low Extent and '4' for Very High Extent:

Option	Description	Statistical Limit
4	Very High Extent	3.50 – 4.00
3	High Extent	2.50 – 3.49
2	Low Extent	1.50 – 2.59
1	Very Low Extent	1.00 – 1.49

The questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for checking and validation.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the approval of the SFAC President thru the managing director for using the name of the school in the research study and for the distribution of the questionnaire to the selected campuses.

Upon approval, the researcher then sent letters to the principal of the selected campuses to allow the researcher to distribute the questionnaires to the respondents after one of their general meetings to ensure immediate retrieval of the questionnaires and its confidentiality and to have a short interview with them at their most convenient time.

Data gathered were tallied by the researcher using a frequency distribution table. Data tallied were then analyzed, interpreted, and presented with the help of a statistician.

Results and Discussion

Table 1
Overall Assessment of the Teacher-Respondents on the Motivation and Hygiene Factors

Criteria	Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
Motivation Factors			
Achievement	3.34	High Extent	5
Advancement	3.38	High Extent	4
Work Itself	3.41	High Extent	3
Recognition	3.06	High Extent	10
Growth	3.42	High Extent	2
Hygiene Factors			
Company Policy	3.12	High Extent	8
Relationship with Peers	3.43	High Extent	1
Work Security	3.32	High Extent	6
Relationship with Supervisor	3.17	High Extent	7
Money	2.66	High Extent	11
Working Conditions	3.08	High Extent	9
Overall Mean	2.53	High Extent	

Legend: Very High Extent 3.50-4.00; High Extent 2.50-3.49; Low Extent 1.50-2.49; Very Low Extent 1.00-1.49

Table 1 shows the overall assessment of the respondents on the motivation and hygiene factors. The results reveal that Relationship with Peer with the overall mean of 3.43 motivates the teacher-respondents at a high extent. This also implies that the teacher-respondents' relationship with their peers is the factor that causes them to be most motivated in their job. Also, Kingir and Mescib (2010) concluded that different opinions between the employees in terms of behavioral statements which can be "Social opportunities provided at the highest level with working period lead the employee to achieve their goals of the organization." Therefore, a social opportunity for the employee is used to boost their motivation level and ultimately helps in achieving the goals and objectives of the organization. Moreover, Growth with an overall mean of 3.42 and Work Itself with an overall mean of 3.41 were considered as 2nd and 3rd most motivating factors for the teacher-respondents, respectively. Both statements got an interpretation of "High Extent". Incessantly, Money got the lowest overall mean of 2.66 and the interpretation of "High Extent". According to Park (2010), monetary incentive acts as a stimulus for greater action and inculcates zeal and enthusiasm toward work, it helps an employee in recognition of achievement. Likewise, Beretti, Figuières, and Grolleau (2013) discussed that monetary incentives used to build a positive environment and maintain a job interest, which is consistent among the employee and offer a spur or zeal in the employees for better performance. Furthermore, Working Conditions with a mean of 3.08 was included in the bottom 3 (rank 9) and got an interpretation of 9. In the study made by Jung and Kim (2012), it stated that a good working environment and good working conditions can increase employee job satisfaction and employee commitment. Thus, employees will try to give their best which can increase the employee work performance if they can feel they are at a company with good working conditions. Recognition with a mean of 3.06, though interpreted as "High Extent", was also included in the bottom 3 (rank 10). Mahazril, et al. (2012) concluded that rewards and recognition, and communication may motivate them to work. Recognition enhances the level of productivity and performance at a job whether it is a first-time performance or a repeated action at the job in a progressive way and ultimately reinforces the behavior of the employee. Generally, for the teacher-respondents, the motivation and hygiene factors motivate them at a "High Extent" based on the overall mean of 3.22. The data also implies that there is a need to improve the working conditions, recognition policy, and the monetary incentives of the institutions since the teacher-respondents were not that motivated with these factors being offered by the institution.

Table 2
Overall Teachers' Performance

COMPONENTS	5	4	3	2	1	MEAN	INTERPRETATION	RANK
Teaching Performance	8	88	0	0	0	4.08	Very Satisfactory	8
Outstanding Accomplishment	5	17	2	22	50	2.01	Fair	10
Participation in Activities	43	46	7	0	0	4.38	Very Satisfactory	6

Attendance in School	55	32	7	2	0	4.46	Very Satisfactory	3
Attendance in Seminars	44	21	31	0	0	4.14	Very Satisfactory	7
External Marketing Efforts	66	16	9	1	4	4.45	Very Satisfactory	4
Submission of Requirements	67	29	0	0	0	4.70	Excellent	1
Students' Achievement	3	84	9	0	0	3.94	Satisfactory	9
Students' Evaluation	55	40	1	0	0	4.56	Excellent	2
Personality Traits	39	56	1	0	0	4.40	Very Satisfactory	5
AVERAGE						4.11	Very Satisfactory	

Legend: Excellent 4.5-5.0; Very Satisfactory 4.0-4.49; Satisfactory 3.5-3.99; Fair 2.25-3.49; Poor 1 – 2.24

Table 2 presents the Overall Teacher's Performance of the three campuses. It reveals that Submission of Requirements garnered the highest mean of 4.70 and the interpretation of "Excellent". Also, Students' Evaluation with a mean of 4.56 got the interpretation of "Excellent" and landed at rank number 2. Attendance in School with a mean of 4.46 ranked 3rd and was interpreted as "Very Satisfactory". Consistently, the Outstanding Accomplishment got the lowest mean of 2.01 and the interpretation of "Fair". On the other hand, the Teaching Performance with a mean of 4.08, and Students' Achievement with a mean of 3.94 were ranked 8th and 9th, respectively. Callo (2015) considered teachers' performance as one of the most important components in academic functions. As an output, the effectiveness or efficiency of performance may be attributed to how much an individual teacher in the school is motivated to perform his tasks well. Generally, the overall teacher's performance of the three big campuses of SFAC is "Very Satisfactory" based on the overall mean of 4.11. However, there is a need to improve the teaching performance of the teachers to also increase the students' achievement. This can be done through an improved motivational strategies to be used in schools. This was backed-up by the study of Srivastava and Barmola (2011) who asserted that extrinsic motivation such as pay, wages, bonuses, and other incentives were very important to increase employees' productivity.

Table 3
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Motivation Factors when Grouped According to Age

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept Ho
Motivation	Between Groups	0.49	3	0.16	4.39	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.93	52	0.04			
	Total	2.42	55				
Hygiene	Between Groups	0.65	3	0.22	2.81	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	4.64	60	0.08			
	Total	5.29	63				

Table 3 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment on the respondents on the motivational factors when grouped according to age. Results show there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation Factors ($F(3,52)=4.39 > cv=2.84$) and the Hygiene Factors ($F(3,30)=2.81 > cv=2.76$) when grouped according to age. Reject H_0 if $F \geq cv$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the motivational factors vary when grouped according to age. As confirmed in the study of McLeod (2018), younger people are more likely to feel motivated by goals, money and enthusiasm from others, whereas older generations are more inspired by their partners, family and nature.

Table 4
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Motivation Factors when Grouped According to Civil Status

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept Ho
Motivation	Between Groups	1.70	2	0.85	14.84	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	2.23	39	0.06			

	Total	3.93	41				
Hygiene	Between Groups	3.86	2	1.93	6.59	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	13.19	45	0.29			
	Total	17.05	47				

Table 4 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment on the respondents on the motivational factors when grouped according to civil status. Results show there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation Factors ($F(2,39)=14.84 > cv=3.23$) and the Hygiene Factors ($F(2,45)=6.59 > cv=3.23$) when grouped according to civil status. Reject H_0 if $F \geq cv$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the motivational factors vary when grouped according to civil status.

Table 5
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Motivation Factors when Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept H_0
Motivation	Between Groups	0.90	3	0.30	1.69	>0.05	Accept
	Within Groups	9.25	52	0.18			
	Total	10.15	55				
Hygiene	Between Groups	1.13	3	0.38	1.38	>0.05	Accept
	Within Groups	16.31	60	0.27			
	Total	17.44	63				

Shown in Table 5 is results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment on the respondents on the motivational factors when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Results show there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation Factors ($F(3,52)=1.69 > cv=2.84$) and the Hygiene Factors ($F(3,60)=1.38 > cv=2.76$) when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Reject H_0 if $F \geq cv$; otherwise, accept H_0 . Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means, regardless of the highest educational attainment, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the motivational factors.

Table 6
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Motivation Factors when Grouped According to Length of Service

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept H_0
Motivation	Between Groups	2.75	4	0.69	12.34	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	3.62	65	0.06			
	Total	6.37	69				
Hygiene	Between Groups	5.25	4	1.31	3.67	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	26.81	75	0.36			
	Total	32.06	79				

Shown in Table 6 is the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment on the respondents on the motivational factors when grouped according to length of service. Results show there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation Factors ($F(4,65)=12.34 > cv=2.53$) and the Hygiene Factors ($F(4,75)=3.67 > cv=2.53$) when grouped according to length of service. Reject H_0 if $F \geq cv$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the motivational factors vary when grouped according to length of service.

Table 7
Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) on the Relationship Between the Motivational Factors and the Teachers' Performance

Area	r-value	crit value	Decision	Remarks
Motivation	0.356	0.9969	Accept H_0	Not significant
Hygiene	0.6809	0.9969	Accept H_0	Not significant

Shown in Table 7 is the presents the results of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) test which measured if motivational factors have a significant effect on the teachers' performance. Results show that there is a low positive correlation between the motivation factors ($r=0.356$, $cv=0.9969$) and the teachers'

performance. Also, there is a positive moderate correlation relationship between the hygiene factors ($r=0.680$, $cv=0.9969$) and the teachers' performance. Further, the data show that there is no significant relationship between the motivational factors, both motivation factors ($r=0.356 < cv=0.9969$) and hygiene factors ($r=0.680 < cv=0.9969$), and the teachers' performance. Reject H_0 if $r \geq cv$; otherwise, accept H_0 . Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. There was no enough evidence to conclude that the relationship was significant.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

Though majority of the teacher-respondents are 20-30 years old, single, college graduate; and, have only rendered 5 years and below in the institution, they still have the maturity to provide credible assessment on the motivational factors considered by the principals.

The results of the study revealed that regardless of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service, the teacher-respondents' assessment on the motivational factors showed that the motivation and hygiene factors motivate them at a high extent with Money as the least motivating factor for the teacher-respondents. Moreover, when grouped according to civil status, the single and married teacher-respondents were motivated at a high extent while the separated teacher-respondents were motivated at a very high extent by the motivation and hygiene factors. Still, Money was still considered as the least motivating factor in this group. The overall teacher's performance of the three big campuses of SFAC is very satisfactory; however, there is a need to improve the teaching performance of the teachers to also increase the students' achievement.

There are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation and Hygiene factors when grouped according to age. There are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation and Hygiene factors when grouped according to civil status. There are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation and Hygiene factors when grouped according to highest educational attainment. There are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the Motivation and Hygiene factors when grouped according to length of service. There is no significant relationship between the motivational factors and the teachers' performance.

A faculty development plan is needed to enhance the teaching performance of the teachers to also increase the students' achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented. First, the teachers should attend different seminars, trainings, and workshops about their specialization to widen their knowledge and enhance their skills regarding their subject matter. The teachers must also make innovations in their field of specialization: instructional materials, curriculum, assessments, and others that can be adopted by all campuses of SFAC. The teachers must also exert more effort in the delivery of content, strategies which includes the instructional materials, and assessments to increase the students' achievement. This can be possible when they continue their professional education. Aside from that, continuing professional education will also open the opportunity for teacher-respondents to conduct timely and relevant researches.

Next, the principals should show support to their teachers; give importance to their relationship with them; and become a trustworthy leaders to them. The principals should also support their teachers in terms of their outstanding accomplishments and attendance in seminars

Moreover, the school management should implement a faculty development plan which focuses on the teachers' performance enhancement. The school management should acquire more resources that support the teachers' innovations and researches.

This study can be replicated by employing a larger population or sample. Future researchers may include all the campuses of SFAC where teachers and other staff will be included in the study. Also, future researchers may consider the use of other methodologies like qualitative research or a case study to find out more in-depth insights into how private schools motivate their employees.

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